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Analysis Of Glucose As A Result Of Diet And Various Types Of Food With Effect Of Physical Activities On Diabetic Patient

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Abstract

A major problem facing diabetics patients is inability to stick to the right diet as they cay on with their daily activities. Due to this, there is need to be diet conscious and engage with some physical activities that ae helpful for the stability of sugar level in their body system, because these are important towards the state of their well-being. The mathematical models were built to decide a diet plan as optimal solution which satisfy all the requirements and restrictions. Although some foods were traced to be the causes of and reoccurrence of high sugar level of diabetes patients and this has brought the need to investigate the different factors that are affecting glucose metabolism. The governing equation was solved directly and analyzed with Maple 18 software. The results shown that as the concentration of insulin increases in the body system of a diabetic patient, the glucose concentration levels reduce. Also, when the body is highly active the glucose level also reduces. In conclusion, the generated results show that, continuous administration of insulin, will reduce the patient's glucose level and assist in increasing the life span of diabetic patients. The results generated were in agreement with related papers.

Keywords: Glucose Concentration, Insulin Concentration, Epinephrine, physical Exercise and Diets.

INTRODUCTION

Insulin is a chemical messenger that allows cells to absorb glucose, a sugar, from the blood. The pancreas is an organ behind the stomach that is the main source of insulin in the body. Clusters of cells in the pancreas called islets produce the hormone and determine the amount based on blood glucose levels in the body. The higher the level of glucose, the more insulin goes into production to balance sugar levels in the blood. Insulin also assists in breaking down fats or proteins for energy. The kind of flow can be in form of continuous drops in the body system called microdroplets, (Badejo et al., 2015, Usman et al., 2015, Badejo et al., 2024). The hormone potentially coordinates with glucagon to modulate blood glucose levels; insulin acts via an anabolic pathway, while glucagon performs catabolic functions. Insulin regulates glucose levels in the bloodstream and induces glucose storage in the liver, muscles, and adipose tissue, resulting in overall weight gain. the protective effects of insulin signaling activators against disease Rahman et al., (2014). Badejo et al., (2019) Usman et al., (2019) and Badejo et al., (2024) addressed the effects of reactive flow in the rotating concentric cylinders which is similar to the fluid flow in the body system, this with eventually affect the movement of the absorbed food like glucose in the body system.

A delicate balance of insulin regulates blood sugar and many processes in the body. If insulin levels are too low or high, excessively high or low blood sugar can start to cause symptoms. If a state of low or high blood sugar continues, serious health problems might start to develop. Noguchi et al., (2014) propose a mathematical model of glucose-insulin metabolism in type 1 diabetes based on Bergman and Shimoda insulin models and the proposed model is able to represent postprandial blood glucose excursion for carbohydrates with varying glucose values. It yielded a considerable degree of accuracy to represent postprandial state for different types of carbohydrate rich foods, which was confirmed by simulation results and it was validated with clinical data. Disappearance of glucose due to insulin action as well as the disappearance of glucose due to tissue uptake such as the brain and nerve cells with rise in glucose level due to infusion through meal intake, oral glucose intake, continuous nutrition absorption and constant infusion Hussain et al., (2014).

In some people, the immune system attacks the islets, and they cease to produce insulin or do not produce enough. When this occurs, blood glucose stays in the blood and cells cannot absorb them to convert the sugars into energy. This is the onset of type 1 diabetes, and a person with this version of diabetes will need regular shots of insulin to survive. The glucose level decreases by the effect of physical activities in daily life routine of a diabetic person, Singh et al., (2021). Adequate diet is of crucial importance, with appropriate use of vitamins, minerals, proteins and other nutrients paying attention to possible beneficial effects of certain foods, adjusted to the skin type, Mirjana et al., (2018). Usman et al., (2020) investigated the effect load on the Foot bridge with compressive Forces, indicating that there is need to consider and put to check the amount of food or diet to be consumed when taking meal as a diabetic patient. The expenditure of the food menu can be minimized by allowing the integer programming approach. Besides ensuring the healthy diet which gives all the essential minerals and vitamins, the feasible solution also made for the eczema patients to plan their diet menu according to the model, Sheng et al., (2017). Diabetes is the disorder of glucose metabolism in which oxidation of sugar does not take place to produce energy due to lack of insulin, Katiyar et al., (2009).

In some people, especially those who are overweight, obese, or inactive, insulin is not effective in transporting glucose into the cells and unable to fulfil its actions. The inability of insulin to exert its effect on tissues is called insulin resistance. Type 2 diabetes will develop when the islets cannot produce enough insulin to overcome insulin resistance. Since the early 20th century, doctors have been able to isolate insulin and provide it in an injectable form to supplement the hormone for people who cannot produce it themselves or have increased insulin resistance. The adoption of western lifestyle with decreased physical activity and more consumption of fast food, the rate of increasing obesity has become tripled Metha et al., (2009).

Insulin is a vital hormone that controls how cells and tissues absorb energy as well as the breakdown of fats and proteins. Clusters of cells in the pancreas called islets secrete this hormone. When cells in the body respond less to its instructions, insulin resistance is increasing. In some people, the immune system attacks the islets, halting insulin production and leading to type 1 diabetes. Type 2 diabetes occurs when insulin resistance coexists with a lack of compensatory increase in insulin production. People can take insulin shots to counteract the effects of insulin resistance. There are fast, intermediate, and long-acting insulin that a person would take depending on how quickly they need to see a drop in blood sugar and the duration for which a person needs to control blood sugar. Physical activities and intake of limited calories to diabetic patients should be encouraged by the medical practitioners, Adamu *et al.*, (2014).

Over the years, diabetes has become a serious challenge to everyone due to the fact that the causes cannot be traced. Recently, treatment measures have been made to individuals living with diabetes to live their normal lives but subject to some classes of foods. That's why this work addresses the contents of food and activities that can reduce the glucose level in a diabetic patient.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mathematical Model

The mathematical model that comprised Glucose (G), Insulin (I) and Epinephrine (E) were adopted with their masses (m_1 to m_9). Some parameters like that of physical exercise in increasing the utilization of glucose and physical exercise in accelerating the utilization of insulin have been considered in model. The model is given as:

$$\frac{dG}{dt} = -(m_1 + e_G)G - m_2I + m_3E + \frac{G_{ext}}{V} \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = m_4G - (m_5 - e_I)I + m_6E \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = -m_7G - m_8I + m_9E \tag{3}$$

Listed below are the parameters and variables values used in the differential equations with discriptions

G - Blood glucose concentration.

I - Blood insulin concentration.

E - Epinephrine.

e_G - Effects of physical exercise in increasing the utilization of glucose.

e_I - Effects of physical exercise in accelerating the utilization of insulin.

V - Volume distribution space

m_1, m_2, \dots, m_9 are constants.

Differentiating equation (1) w.r.t.t to yields

$$\frac{d^2G}{dt^2} = -(m_1 + e_G)\frac{dG}{dt} - m_2\frac{dI}{dt} + m_3\frac{dE}{dt} \tag{4}$$

Substituting both equations (2) and (3) into (4) result into

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2G}{dt^2} + (m_1 + e_G)\frac{dG}{dt} + (m_2m_4 + m_3m_7)G - (m_2m_5 + m_2e_I - m_3m_8)I - (m_6 + m_3m_9)E \\ = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Reducing equation (5) to

$$\frac{d^2G}{dt^2} + \gamma \frac{dG}{dt} + \alpha G = 0 \tag{6}$$

When, $\gamma = m_1 + e_G$, $\alpha = m_2m_4 + m_3m_7$, $Q = (m_2m_5 + m_2e_I - m_3m_8)I + (m_6 + m_3m_9)E$

Let

$$\frac{d^2G}{dt^2} = m^2, \quad \frac{dG}{dt} = m, \quad m^0 = G$$

Therefore, equation (6) yields

$$m^2 + Ym + \alpha = 0 \tag{7}$$

Equation (7) results to

$$m = \frac{-1}{2} Y \pm \frac{\sqrt{Y^2 - 4\alpha}}{2} \Rightarrow m = \alpha \pm \beta x$$

The complimentary function is;

$$G = e^{\alpha x} (A \cos \beta x + iB \sin \beta x) \tag{8}$$

Hence, the general solution yields

$$G(t) = e^{-1/2 Y t} \left(A \cos \frac{\sqrt{Y^2 - 4\alpha}}{2} t + iB \sin \frac{\sqrt{Y^2 - 4\alpha}}{2} t \right) + \frac{Q(t)}{\alpha} \tag{9}$$

Substituting the initial condition into (9) given;

$$Q(0) = 0, t = 0$$

$$G = 1(A) \rightarrow G = A \rightarrow A = 1 \text{ (since } G = 1)$$

Hence,

$$A = 1, \quad B = Y/2$$

The general solution becomes

$$G(t) = e^{-1/2 Y t} \left(\cos(Y^2 - 4\alpha)^{1/2} t + \frac{Y}{2} \sin \left(\frac{(Y^2 - 4\alpha)^{-1/2}}{2} t + \frac{Q(t)}{\alpha} \right) \right)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 4.1 shows the effect of insulin (I) values from 0 to 9 on glucose (G) and it was observed that as the insulin increases glucose decreases from positive value to negative indicating that administering of insulin can reduce the level of glucose in the body system of diabetic patient.

Fig. 4.2 shows the effect of Epinephrine (E) values from 0 to 9 on glucose (G) and it was observed that as the Epinephrine (E) increases the glucose value also increases. Suggesting that, it cannot reduce the glucose level in the body system.

Fig. 4.3 shows the effect of output of carbohydrate metabolism system (G_{ext}) values from 0 to 9 on glucose (G) and it was observed that as G_{ext} increases the glucose value also increases. Suggesting that it cannot reduce the glucose level in the body system

Table 1

S/N	INSULIN (I)	GLUCOSE (G)
1	0	0.817
2	1	0.4085
3	2	0
4	3	-0.4085
5	4	-0.817
6	5	-1.2255
7	6	-1.634
8	7	-2.0425
9	8	-2.451
10	9	-2.8595

Table 2

S/N	EPINEPHRINE(E)	GLUCOSE (G)
1	0	0
2	1	0.4085
3	2	0.817
4	3	1.2255
5	4	1.634
6	5	2.0425
7	6	2.451
8	7	2.8595
9	8	3.268
10	9	3.6765

Table 2

S/N	G (OUTPUT)	GLUCOSE (G)
1	0	0
2	1	0.4085
3	2	0.817
4	3	1.2255
5	4	1.634
6	5	2.0425
7	6	2.451
8	7	2.8595
9	8	3.268
10	9	3.6765

Summary

Tables above show the effects of insulin (I), output of carbohydrate metabolism system (G_{ext}) and Epinephrine (E) on glucose and it was observed that as the values of insulin increases the values of glucose reduces suggesting that continuous administering or intake of insulin to the system of a diabetic patient minimize glucose level.

The effect of Epinephrine (E) shows that glucose increases as the Epinephrine (E) values increases, indicating Epinephrine (E), determine high level of glucose in the body system sometimes.

Insulin values from 0 to 9 on Epinephrine was observed as insulin increases it shows that Epinephrine reduces in value but all in negative form. Indicating that insulin does not has effect on Epinephrine in the body system of diabetic patients.

CONCLUSION

The continuous administering or intake of insulin, to the system of a diabetic patient minimizes glucose level.

Epinephrine (E) determines high level of glucose in the body system sometimes.

Output of carbohydrate metabolism system (G_{ext}) determine the level of glucose in the body system since both have positive relationship.

High level of secretion of this Adrenaline hormone may reduce the functions of insulin in the body system and this is not good for diabetic patients.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Diabetic patients should reduce the intake or consumption of carbohydrate food.

Body activity should be recommended for diabetic patients on daily bases.

Intake of insulin must be continuous for diabetic patient.

Diabetic patients should always go for regular checkup.

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